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“HANDS OF DEDICATION: A VOYAGE IN WHITE”

Dress in the form of white
Knowledge lingered with might
As he overcomes the height,
Of being great through the night.

As the clock meets its moribund
Strength and courage were found
As the orison and pleas hovered around
A canopy for his apprentices sculped a sound

His eyes were filled with great determination,
As he carried the weights of predicament
Though his amygdala whispered him to lament
He mourned without relinquishing seeds of dedication

As the seeds that he sowed thrive in the storms
Watered by the wisdom he honed,
Trees of dexterity he incessantly forms
With adept hands, he glided from the thorns

His witticism created a surreal camaraderie,
A form of escapism from the paradox
and distress of reverie

Without him, being cognizant that he is a part of a great memory.